

TABLE 1—IR SPECTRA OF COMPOUNDS (cm⁻¹)

Sl. no.	Compounds	ν_{OH}	δ_{I-OH}	δ_{H_2O}	δ_{I-OH}	ν_{I-O}	$\tau_{I-O(H)}$	ν_{I-O-I}	δ_{O-I-O}	δ_{I-O-I}	Additional peaks
1.	H ₂ [Fe ₂ I ₂ O ₈ .H ₁₂]	3410-3490s,b	-	1650m	1360w	687m,b	-	-	500vs 420s 300s 230m 220m 475s 400s 255m 235m 215m	-	850m
2.	Na ₂ [Fe(H ₂ IO ₆) ₂ (OH) ₂].6H ₂ O	3540 3480 3400vs	2250w	1635, 1615m	1380w 1150w 1015sh	615s	-	-	475s 400s 255m 235m 215m	-	-
3.	H ₂ [Co ₂ I ₂ O ₈ .H ₁₂].6H ₂ O	3350-2600	2230 v,w	1530m	1130w 1080w	780s 670m 575m 550m	-	-	475m 350s 290sh 275sh	-	-
4.	Na ₂ [Co(H ₂ IO ₆) ₂ (OH) ₂].8H ₂ O	3600-3100s,b	2260w	1610-1595m	1300m 1270w 1165sh 1080w	770s 720w 630w	880w	-	530w,b 390w 340w 320w 300w 255sh	-	-
5.	Li ₂ [NiI ₂ O ₈].6H ₂ O	3500-3360s,b	-	1650m	-	710m,b	-	600w	-	450m,b	-
6.	NaCeIO ₆ .H ₂ O	3380-3110s,b	2380m	1600-1575w,b	1460w	700-670s,b]	-	-	450-420m,b 370vw 210m,s	-	-
7.	Li ₁₀ [UO ₂ I ₂ O ₈].8H ₂ O	3400s,b	2200w	1640w,b	1390m	720-650vs,b	-	-	480-400vs,b 285w 220w	-	880m
8.	Li ₇ [Ga(IO ₆) ₂].4H ₂ O	3520-3430m	-	1640w,b	-	700s 620s	-	-	310sh 235w 215w	-	-
9.	Ga ₂ (IO ₆) ₂ .H ₂ O	3500-3080s,b	2320w	1625-1600m,b	1380s 1170-1035w,b	720-650m,b	-	-	480s 385m 290s 250m	-	940w

vs = very strong, s = strong, m = medium, sh = shoulder, b = broad, vw = very weak.

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Synthesis and Studies on Some Mixed-Metal Periodates of Cerium(IV)

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MIXED metal periodates of the type M^IM^{IV}IO₆ (M^I=Na, K, NH₄, Rb, Cs, and M^{IV}=Ni, Mn, Pb, Ce, Sn) are known¹⁻⁴. Periodate of nickel(IV) was first prepared¹ followed² by Ni^{IV} and Mn^{IV}. The compounds of lead, germanium and

tin have been prepared recently³⁻⁴. Although ceric periodates are known⁵⁻⁸, preparation of mixed metal ceriperiodates has not been attempted so far. This is for the first time that mixed metal rare-earth periodates have been prepared and their properties studied. The work of Alimarin *et al.*⁷ was repeated for the preparation of potassium ceriperiodate, but we were unsuccessful. Some studies on $\text{CeHfO}_6 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ have also been carried out.

Experimental

Ceric hydrogen periodate: $\text{CeHfO}_6 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$: NaIO_4 was added to a solution of ceric ammonium nitrate maintained at pH 1.15-1.50. The freshly prepared compound was dissolved in excess KOH (3 N) containing NaIO_4 . To this was added a concentrated solution of sodium nitrate and stirred well. A light yellow precipitate settled, washed with water to free it from alkali, cerium and nitrate ions, kept in a vacuum desiccator for 48 h and stored over conc. H_2SO_4 . The composition $\text{NaCeIO}_6 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ was in consistent with the percentages found.

The same compound was also prepared by stirring $\text{CeHfO}_6 \cdot \text{XH}_2\text{O}$ vigorously with caustic soda solution (50 ml, 3 N) for about 12 h at 35-40°. The yellow product was filtered, washed with methanol and water and finally dried over conc. H_2SO_4 .

Lithium ceriperiodate: Ceric ammon nitrate (40 ml, 0.274M), KIO_4 (30 ml, 0.29M) and KOH (30 ml, 17.85M) were mixed in 100 ml KOH (4.46M) and with stirring lithium nitrate was added. The light yellow product was washed with aqueous methanol (1:1) and dried over conc. H_2SO_4 . The formula of the compound was found to be $\text{LiCeIO}_6 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Potassium ceriperiodate: Aqueous methanol (1:1) was added to the solution of $\text{CeHfO}_6 \cdot \text{XH}_2\text{O}$ in KOH (3 N) and the resulting precipitated product was washed successively with water, methanol and ether.

Magnetic susceptibility was measured in a Gouy magnetic balance at 29°. Uv spectra were recorded on a Varian Techtron automatic recording spectrophotometer and the visible spectra on a Hilger UNISPEK spectrophotometer. Mull spectra were taken using liquid paraffin as base. Spectra of $\text{CeHfO}_6 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was taken in KOH solution (3 N). Ir spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer and Unicam SP 1000 spectrophotometer. X-Ray diffractograms were recorded on a Philips PW 1140 diffractometer using Fe-K_α radiation. Thermal studies were carried out on a Paulik-Paulik-Erdey MOM OD-102 derivetograph using platinum crucible at the heating rate 3°min^{-1} .

Results and Discussion

Uv and visible spectra: The results of the spectral data are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF THE COMPOUNDS

Compounds	λ_{max} nm	$\nu \times 10^4$	Intensity*	Assignment**
$\text{NaCeIO}_6 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	430	2.32	m	CT
	207	4.83	vs	CT
$\text{LiCeIO}_6 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	430	2.32	m	CT
	195	5.12	vs	CT
$\text{CeHfO}_6 \cdot \text{XH}_2\text{O}$	425	2.35	m	CT
	200	5.00	vs	CT
$\text{CeHfO}_6 \cdot \text{XH}_2\text{O}$ in 3N KOH	400	2.50	s	CT
	360-290	(2.77-3.44)	h	CT
	220	4.54	vs	CT

*m = medium, vs = very strong, s = strong, h = hump.

**CT = charge transfer.

The peaks around 400 nm are due to metal-ligand charge transfer and those around 200 nm are characteristic of 10_6^{5-} species. The appearance of an absorption maxima at 300 nm was noted for a ceric periodate complex in alkaline medium⁹.

Ir spectra: Strong and broad band at 3500-2800 cm^{-1} (stretching OH) is due to hydrogen bonding of the type O-H...O. Deformation vibrations of water molecules occur at higher values for the sodium, potassium and lithium salts. The number of bands are three with the alkali metal salts and only one with the ceric periodate. I-OH vibration occurring at higher wave number for the mixed-metal periodates may be due to strengthening of this bond. The bands at 2350 cm^{-1} may be assigned to 2δ (I-OH) vibration¹⁰. Similarly, I-O bond seems stronger for the metal periodates. The results are shown in the Table 2.

X-Ray diffractogram: The results show the compounds to be of amorphous variety. Two halos are observed for $\text{CeHfO}_6 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{LiCeIO}_6 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ but only one for $\text{NaCeIO}_6 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. The halo for the sodium salt starts from 30° and extends upto 45° corresponding to d value of 3.74 and 2.53 Å, respectively. The peak values correspond to a plane of interplaner spacing 3.01 Å. For the lithium salt the first halo starts from 20° (d=5.58 Å) and extends upto 31.3° (d=3.59 Å), with the peak value d = 4.44 Å. The second halo starts from 53° (d=2.17 Å) and extends upto 58.5° (d=1.98 Å), with the peak value d=2.09 Å. For $\text{CeHfO}_6 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, the first halo extends from 27° (d=4.15 Å) to 37° (d=3.05 Å), corresponding to a peak value d = 3.54 Å. The second halo extends from 38° (d=2.98 Å) to 49° (d = 2.34 Å) corresponding to the peak value d=2.53 Å.

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRA OF COMPOUNDS

CeHIO ₆ ·4H ₂ O	NaCeIO ₆ ·H ₂ O	LiCeIO ₆ ·H ₂ O	KCeIO ₆ ·XH ₂ O	Assignment
3500-2830s, b 2370-2320w, b 1610s	3380-3100s, b 2380m 1600-1575w, b	3500-3240s, b 2380m 1650m 1560m 1540m 14·0w 1420w 1340b, w 1060b, w 780s, b 720-680s, b	3500-3200s, b 2340m 1650m 1555m 1540m 1460w 1450w 1330w	ν_{OH} $2\delta_{IOH}$ δ_{H_2O}
1300w 1160w	1460w			δ_{IOH}
720s 690-670b 560m 420s 350s 270sh	700-670s, b 450-420m, b 370w 220m, s		750-680s, b	δ_{IO} ν_{IOH} δ_{OIO}

s = strong, b = broad, w = weak, m = medium.

Thermal study : The results of thermal study are shown below.

The compound CeHIO₆·4H₂O was found to be stable upto 60°. The product obtained at 270° was CeHIO₆·H₂O which was stable upto 310°. The product CeHIO₆ was stable at 360-445°. CeO₂ was obtained as residue after 620°. LiCeIO₆·H₂O was found to be stable upto 70°. Loss of water molecules took place at 70-145°, followed by a gradual loss in weight. The product obtained at 580° was a mixture of LiI and CeO₂. After 1000° it became Li₂O and CeO₂. NaCeIO₆·H₂O was stable upto 55° followed by gradual loss of water upto 280°. The end product obtained after 720° was a mixture of Na₂O and CeO₂.

The compounds are all yellow. The deepening of colour of the compounds follows the order, Li < Na < K. The solubility of the salts in water is of the order K > Na > Li.

The compounds behaved as oxidising agents in dilute sulphuric acid medium and oxidised three

moles of Mohr salt per mole of the compound corresponding to the reduction of Ce^{IV} to Ce^{III} and of periodate to iodate, and consumed nine-equivalents of sodium thiosulphate per mole of the compound to titrate the liberated iodine when potassium iodide was added to the H₂SO₄ solution.

Potentiometric titration with Mohr salt could not be carried out with the H₂SO₄ solution of these compounds.

The calculated molar susceptibility values, -68.19 × 10⁻⁶ for sodium salt and -47.79 × 10⁻⁶ for lithium salt confirmed the compounds to be diamagnetic.

Thermal studies have confirmed that the compounds are of equal stability and are stable at the room temperature. The end product is CeO₂ for ceric periodate and is a mixture of CeO₂ and alkali metal. CeHIO₆ is stable over a wide range of temperature.

Infrared spectral studies have confirmed the presence of stretching and bending vibrations of OH, I-OH, H₂O, I-O, IO-(H) and OIO groups. Hydrogen bondings are also present. Appearance of peaks nearly in the same region show similarity in the structures of the mixed-metal periodates. The arrangement of six oxygen atoms round iodine may not be symmetrical as more peaks appear in the δ_{IOH} and δ_{OIO} vibrations¹¹. X-Ray study reveals that the compounds are amorphous.

Electronic spectra confirm the presence of IO₆⁵⁻ in all these compounds¹². The shift in absorption maxima in this region, may be due to the size effect of the alkali metals in the IO₆⁵⁻ environment. Appearance of absorption maxima at 430 nm in

all three compounds indicates their structural similarity.

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Potentiometric Studies of Some Cerium(IV) and Dysprosium(III) Complexes

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THE present work was carried out to study the complexing properties of cerium(IV) and dysprosium(III) with 1-cyclohexyldene-2-benzylidene succinic acid (CHBSA), 1-cyclohexyldene succinic acid (CHSA), and 1-phenyl-3-thiobenzoyl thiocarbamide (PTT) at a fixed ionic strength and temperature. The communication reports for the first time the proton-ligand stability constants of all the three ligands and the metal-ligand stability constants of the complexes of CHBSA and CHSA with both cerium and dysprosium. The method used was the Bjerrum-Calvin titration technique^{1,2} as adapted by Irving and Rossotti³.

Experimental

Reagents: Stock solutions ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) of both cerium and dysprosium were prepared using ceric ammonium sulphate (AR, SM) and dysprosium chloride (Indian Rare Earths) in calculated quantity of perchloric acid solution to prevent hydrolysis.

All the three ligands, namely CHBSA⁴, CHSA⁴ and PTT^{5,6} were prepared and purified. The stock solutions ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) of CHBSA and CHSA were prepared in alcohol and PTT in acetone. The solutions of the ligands were prepared by suitable dilution of the stock solutions so that ligands were present in 30% alcoholic or acetone solution. The ligands solutions were standardized potentiometrically.

Sodium hydroxide pellets (EM) were dissolved in CO₂-free distilled water and kept overnight. A portion of it was diluted and its concentration determined by titrating it potentiometrically against standard potassium hydrogen phthalate (0.1M).

The stock solution of perchloric acid (EM) (0.1M) was prepared and standardized potentiometrically with a standard sodium hydroxide solution.

Potassium chloride (AnalaR) solution (1.0M) was used to maintain the ionic strength of the system and was prepared by dissolving a known weight in CO₂-free distilled water.

Apparatus: Elico pH meter (sensitivity ± 0.05) with glass-calomel electrode system was used for pH measurements. The pH meter was calibrated by a suitable buffer before use. All experiments were carried out at room temperature (27°).

Bjerrum-Calvin titration:

The three mixtures were prepared as follows: (A) 10 ml $10^{-1} M$ HClO₄ + 80 ml double distilled water + 10 ml M KCl solution, (B) 10 ml $10^{-1} M$ HClO₄ + 10 ml $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand solution + 20 ml redistilled acetone/alcohol + 10 ml M KCl solution + 50 ml double distilled water, and (C) 10 ml $10^{-1} M$ HClO₄ + 10 ml $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand solution + 20 ml redistilled acetone/alcohol + 10 ml $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal ion solution + 10 ml M KCl solution + 40 ml double distilled water. These solutions were titrated with a standard sodium hydroxide solution. The three curves obtained by plotting pH against the volume of alkali added were referred to as (a) acid titration curve, (b) ligand titration curve and (c) complex titration curve.

Results and Discussion

The calculation of practical proton ligand stability constant was carried out by plotting a graph of \bar{n}_A vs pH and applying the method of interpolation at half \bar{n}_A values and interpolation at various \bar{n}_A values. The values with error limit of ± 0.03 are given in Table I